

Synthesis of Substituted Piperazinyl Semicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazide : as Possible Acetyl Cholinesterase(AChE) Inhibitors

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Some new N'-(N-aryl-N'-acetyl) piperazine-N⁴-aryl/alkyl Semicarbazide and Thiosemicarbazides have been synthesised as possible/Acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) Inhibitors, by the condensation of N-aryl N'-piperazine acetic acid hydrazide with aryl or alkyl isocyanate and aryl isothiocyanates.

PIPERAZINE derivatives have been shown to possess diverse biological properties including antihistaminic¹, antimetic² and anticonvulsant^{3,4} activities. Recent studies indicated the anticonvulsant activity of several thiosemicarbazides^{5,6,7} and their ability to inhibit nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) dependent oxidations. Furthermore anticonvulsants are known to inhibit acetyl cholinesterase^{8,9}. This prompted us to synthesis the title compounds with the idea that the combined effect of the piperazine nucleus and >N-C- or

>N-C- $\begin{matrix} \parallel \\ \text{S} \end{matrix}$ might confer much enhanced antiacetyl cholinesterase activity on these compounds.

In all eighteen thiosemicarbazides and six semicarbazides have been prepared according to the tentative scheme given below. The structure given in compound IV is supported by infrared spectroscopy as the peaks of all vital functional groups tally with standard values reported in the literature. Absorption frequencies for -CONHNH, 2900 & 3300 cm^{-1} ; C, 1700 cm^{-1} ; CNH, 1550 cm^{-1} ; NHCS, 1360 cm^{-1} . In the i.r. spectra of all the compounds

listed in Table the peaks for the above functional groups appear nearly at 2940 and 3250 cm^{-1} ; 1700 cm^{-1} ; 1540 cm^{-1} , respectively. Semicarbazides

$\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C} \end{matrix}$ gives sharp peak at about 1640 for -C-NH. Twelve thiosemicarbazides have been evaluated for their antiacetyl cholinesterase activity, however six compounds showed inhibition.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. N-aryl piperazines(I) (R=H, 3-CH₃ & 4-CH₃) were prepared according to known procedures^{10,11}.

1-piperazine acetic acid 4-aryl ethyl ester (II, Table I)

The equimolar quantities of 1-aryl piperazine (0.01 m), K₂CO₃ (0.01 m) (anhydrous) and chloroethylacetate (0.01 m) were taken in 20 ml dry benzene and mixture was refluxed for 8-16 hrs. The reaction time in each case was determined by TLC on silica

gel G. The ester showed R_f values higher than the 1-aryl piperazines. The hot mixture was evaporated and the residue was washed with water and then extracted with benzene, benzene layer was separated and dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$. Now it is concentrated and distilled under reduced pressure.

1-piperazine acetic acid-4-aryl-hydrazides (III, Table 2)

To a solution of .01 mole of ester (II) in 5 ml ethyl alcohol (absolute) was added 0.015 mole of hydrazine hydrate. The mixture was refluxed for 6-12 hrs and reaction time was determined by TLC.

The ester showed R_f value higher than the hydrazides. Ethyl alcohol was evaporated and residue was distilled or crystallised as the case may be.

N'-[(N-aryl-N'-acetyl) piperazine]-N⁴-methylphenyl Semicarbazide or aryl thiosemicarbazide: (IV, Table 3)

A mixture of 0.01 mole of 1-piperazine acetic acid-4-arylhydrazide(III) and 0.01 mole of appropriate isocyanate or isothiocyanate in 30 ml of dry benzene was refluxed on steambath for 4 hours. The reaction mixture cooled and solid mass which separated out was filtered and crystallised from suitable

TABLE 1

S. No.	R.	M. P. °C/Press or B. P. m.m.	Yield %	Molecular formulae	Analysis %		
					Calc.	C H N	Found
1.	H ^a	135-140/3	60	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	C 67.74 H 8.06 N 11.29		67.35 8.00 11.00
2.	2-CH ₃	155-160/3	50	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	C 68.71 H 8.39 N 10.80		68.25 8.10 10.50
3.	3-CH ₃	160-65/3	50	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	C 68.71 H 8.39 N 10.80		69.00 8.20 10.20
4.	4-CH ₃ ^b	57	60	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	C 68.71 H 8.39 N 10.80		68.30 8.30 10.40

a. Lit^{1,2} B. P. 194°C/8 m. m.
b. recrystallised from C₆H₆/Petroleum ether

TABLE 2

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formulae	Analysis %		
					Calc.	C H N	Found
1.	H	75	55	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	C 61.55 H 7.69 N 23.93		61.10 7.20 23.60
2.	2-CH ₃	nil	50	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	C 62.71 H 8.06 N 22.57		62.25 8.00 22.15
3.	3-CH ₃	60	60	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	C 62.71 H 8.06 N 22.57		62.32 8.15 22.35
4.	4-CH ₃	130	65	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	C 62.71 H 8.06 N 22.57		63.00 8.35 22.15

Recrystallising solvent C₆H₆/Petroleum ether

TABLE—3

S. No.	R	R'	X	M.P. °C	Recrystallising solvent	Molecular Formulae	Analysis %		
							Calculated	Found	
1.	H	Phehyl	S	197	ethanol	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₅ OS	C	61.79	62.00
							H	6.23	6.40
							N	18.92	18.50
2.	H	2-Methyl phenyl	S	163	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₅ OS	C	62.66	62.50
							H	6.52	6.00
							N	17.86	18.00
3.	H	3-Methyl phenyl	S	180	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₅ OS	C	62.66	62.76
							H	6.52	6.50
							N	17.86	17.93
4.	H	4-Methyl phenyl	S	168	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₅ OS	C	62.66	63.00
							H	6.52	7.00
							N	17.86	17.40
5.	H	4-Cl-Phenyl	S	194	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ ClN ₅ OS	C	57.41	57.00
							H	5.74	5.76
							N	16.74	17.00
6.	H	4-Br-Phenyl	S	192	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ BrN ₅ OS	C	51.95	52.00
							H	5.19	5.20
							N	15.14	15.60
7.	3-CH ₃	Phenyl	S	162	do	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₅ OS	C	62.66	63.05
							H	6.52	6.42
							N	17.86	17.96
8.	3-CH ₃	2-Methyl phenyl	S	155	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.86
							H	6.88	6.56
							N	17.63	17.40
9.	3-CH ₃	3-Methyl phenyl	S	170	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.96
							H	6.88	6.80
							N	17.63	18.00
10.	3-CH ₃	4-Methyl phenyl	S	172	DMF & ethanol	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.76
							H	6.88	6.38
							N	17.63	17.21
11.	3-CH ₃	4-Cl-phenyl	S	196	ethanol	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ OS	C	58.48	58.00
							H	6.03	5.86
							N	16.23	15.89
12.	3-CH ₃	4-Br-Phenyl	S	187	DMF & ethanol	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ BrN ₅ OS	C	52.94	53.00
							H	5.50	5.14
							N	14.70	14.50
13.	4-CH ₃	Phenyl	S	186	ethanol	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₂	C	62.66	62.18
							H	6.52	6.12
							N	17.86	17.80
14.	4-CH ₃	2-Methyl phenyl	S	172	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.50
							H	6.88	6.48
							N	17.63	18.06
15.	4-CH ₃	3-Methyl phenyl	S	196	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.00
							H	6.88	6.42
							N	17.63	18.00
16.	4-CH ₃	4-Methyl phenyl	S	190	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS	C	63.47	63.15
							H	6.88	7.00
							N	17.63	18.20
17.	4-CH ₃	4-Cl-Phenyl	S	200	DMF & ethanol	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ OS	C	58.48	58.60
							H	6.03	6.25
							N	16.23	16.46
18.	4-CH ₃	4-Br-Phenyl	S	188	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ BrN ₅ OS	C	52.94	52.84
							H	5.50	5.42
							N	14.70	14.84
19.	H	Methyl	O	199	ethanol	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	C	57.62	57.16
							H	7.21	7.11
							N	24.05	23.63
20.	H	Phenyl	O	146	do	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂	C	64.58	65.10
							H	6.51	6.48
							N	19.82	20.15

TABLE—3 (Contd.)

21.	3-CH ₃	Methyl	O	195	do	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₂	C	59.02	58.81
							H	7.54	8.06
							N	22.95	23.15
22.	3-CH ₃	Phenyl	O	155	do	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₂	C	66.50	66.56
							H	9.60	6.36
							N	18.47	18.54
23.	4-CH ₃	Methyl	O	215	do	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₂	C	59.02	59.00
							H	7.54	7.06
							N	22.95	22.45
24.	4-CH ₃	Phenyl	O	181	Benzene	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₂	C	66.50	66.12
							H	6.60	6.60
							N	18.47	18.23

solvent. Physical constants of the compounds thus prepared are listed in the Table.

Biological Data :

Enzyme preparation : Male adult albino rats weighing approximately 200-220 gm. were killed by decapitation. Brains were quickly removed and homogenized in ice-cold 0.25 M sucrose with the help of a Potter-Elvehjem type homogenizer fitted with a teflon pestle.

Determination of acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) activity

The method of Hestrin¹³ as described by Colwick and Kalpan¹⁴ was used. The reaction mixture in a final volume of 1.5 ml contained 0.075 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.4, 4 M acetylcholine and 0.2 ml of 10% (w/v) homogenate. The reaction mixture with or without test compounds was incubated in a constant temperature water bath for 5 minutes after which the reaction was started with the addition of acetylcholine. The reaction was stopped after 10 mins. with the addition of 2 ml of alkaline hydroxylamine reagent (made by mixing equal volumes of 3.5 N NaOH and 2M hydroxylamine within an hour of use). Immediately after the addition of hydroxylamine reagent, 1 ml of cold 4N HCl was added to precipitate the protein as well as to bring the pH sufficiently acidic (pH 1 to 2). After centrifugation (at 500 × g for 5 min) the supernatant was transferred into a separate tube. Colour was developed promptly by adding 1 ml of 0.37 M ferric chloride in 0.1N HCl and intensity of colour was measured at 540 M. All compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol (100%) and used at 3 × 10⁻⁴ M. A control containing equal volume of propylene glycol was also run in parallel. Each assay was done in duplicate.

Results

Compounds from serial number 1 to 18 of Table 3 were tested and six compounds namely 3, 6, 7, 9, 12 and 14 showed marginal inhibition.

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